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CBN Stabilization Policies And Financial Resilience Of The Nigerian Banking Industry

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) stabilization policies on the financial resilience of the Nigerian banking industry from 1993 to 2022. Stabilization policies, measured by lending rate (LER), monetary policy rate (MPR), exchange rate (EXR), and broad money supply (BMS), served as the independent variables, while financial resilience (FIR), captured by the bank z-score, were the dependent variable. Four research hypotheses were developed, and data were sourced from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and World Bank Group statistical reports (2022). The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was employed to analyze the relationship. The results showed that EXR and BMS had positive and significant effects on the FIR of Nigerian banks in both the short and long run. In contrast, LER exerted a negative and significant impact on FIR across both horizons. Although MPR was less emphasized, the findings indicate that lower policy rates generally enhance banking stability. These results highlight the dual role of stabilization policies, with some indicators fostering resilience while others weaken it. The study concludes that maintaining lower LER, stable MPR, and moderate EXR movements improves the resilience of Nigerian banks over time. It recommends that the CBN sustain benchmark interest rates through relatively stable policies, keep lending rates at low levels, preferably single digits, and ensure stability to reduce risks to the banking sector. This research makes a significant contribution to the ongoing debate on the role of the CBN in safeguarding financial stability. By developing a robust empirical model, it explains the interaction between stabilization policies and financial resilience in Nigeria. The findings provide critical policy insights that emphasize interest rate and exchange rate management as key levers for strengthening the banking sector.

Keywords: Stabilization Policies, Lending Rate, Monetary Policy Rate, Exchange Rate, Broad Money Supply Ratio and Financial Resilience

INTRODUCTION

Central banks across the globe play a critical role in maintaining both economic and financial stability. Traditionally known as lenders of last resort, these institutions have increasingly extended their influence into direct economic involvement, though the degree of intervention varies across countries. In developed economies, quantitative easing and similar programs are commonly employed to stimulate growth and

strengthen bank resilience, while in emerging economies, central banks adopt other stabilization tools suited to their contexts. Within Nigeria, the CBN relies largely on conventional monetary instruments such as interest rates, open market operations, discount rates, and selective credit controls to stabilize the financial system. Its interventions also extend to cooperatives, microfinance institutions, and other community-based credit organizations. The primary objectives of these stabilization policies are to raise national output, curb inflation, and expand financial markets. As Twinoburyo and Odhiambo (2017) emphasized, monetary policy remains an essential tool for salvaging economies from recessions and depressions.

In Nigeria, CBN interventions are carried out through both direct and indirect measures aimed at boosting and diversifying the economy. Emefiele (2015) explained that these involvements, though ancillary to the bank's core mandate, support its developmental role. Key stabilization policies used by the CBN include Open Market Operations (OMO), Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), liquidity ratio, bank rate, broad money supply, exchange rate, lending rate, selective credit control, and moral suasion. Among these instruments, the exchange rate exerts considerable influence due to its effects on currency value, inflation, external balance, capital flows, and overall financial stability (Osakwe et al 2019). Rising exchange rates increase the cost of imports, fueling inflation, while low lending rates can encourage local production but may trigger currency depreciation. Nevertheless, the combined interaction of these policies stimulates investment, consumer spending, production, and employment, thereby enhancing economic resilience.

Economic stability, as defined by Ekechukwu et al (2021), exists when an economy experiences minimal macroeconomic fluctuations, steady growth, and low inflation. To achieve this, the CBN has introduced multiple intervention programs designed to preserve stability within the financial system. By managing interest rates, money supply, and exchange rate dynamics, the apex bank seeks to mitigate instability and ensure resilience in the Nigerian banking sector. Against this backdrop, the present study evaluates the effect of CBN stabilization policies on the financial resilience of Nigeria's banking industry, with particular attention to key growth components.

The effectiveness of central bank stabilization policy instruments remains one of the most debated issues among development economists, monetary experts, and financial analysts. In Nigeria, despite the CBN implementation of various stabilization measures, the economy remains underdeveloped, characterized by persistent budget deficits, inefficient payment systems, and weak banking habits due to large volumes of funds circulating outside the banking system. Comparatively, Nigeria's economic growth lags behind countries like Brazil and South Africa, while ineffective credit delivery to the productive sectors continues to raise doubts about the potency of these policies. Although empirical evidence links CBN stabilization instruments to money supply, loan disbursement, liquidity, deposit base, and banks' ability to perform their financial roles, there is still no consensus on the exact nature of the relationship. Furthermore, most existing studies fail to incorporate key market-based instruments such as the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) and Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) alongside exchange rate, lending rate, and broad money supply within a single model. Prior research has also relied heavily on Johansen cointegration, which is unsuitable for mixed-order stationary variables, while even the ARDL approach employed by Osakwe et al (2019) was limited to the manufacturing sector. This study, therefore, uniquely applies to the Nigerian banking industry to address these gaps.

Conceptual Review

Central Bank of Nigeria Stabilization Policies

Okanyal and Paseda (2019) define CBN stabilization policy instruments as deliberate actions of the monetary authorities, particularly the central bank, aimed at controlling the quantity, availability, or cost of money in an economy to achieve specific objectives. In simpler terms, they are a combination of policy measures designed to regulate money supply and credit cost in line with the expected level of economic activity. Monetary policy, as the central bank's major stabilization tool, involves the regulation of money supply, availability, and cost to meet predetermined national goals. It reflects the deliberate efforts of the apex bank to stabilize the economy and ensure that financial resources are channeled effectively to support growth and stability.

Similarly, Dare and Okeya (2017) conceptualize CBN stabilization instruments as an effective “economic stabilizer” used to determine and influence the quantity and direction of money and credit within an economy in pursuit of key macroeconomic objectives such as employment generation, balance of payments stability, and sustainable economic development. Buckley et al (2018) add that such policies are often deployed to restore depressed economies, while broadly seeking to enhance efficiency, promote financial security, and ensure stability through full employment and controlled inflation. In general, these policies are tailored to achieve specific economic goals, often implemented in combination with fiscal and trade policies to direct the overall trajectory of the economy. As Baker et al (2016) emphasize, monetary stabilization policies not only serve as corrective measures during periods of instability but also provide a framework for fostering long-term growth and resilience in the financial system.

CBN Stabilization Policies Instruments

Monetary Policy Rate: The apex bank extends credit to Deposit Money Banks, influencing their reserve levels and, consequently, the overall monetary base. It provides loans to financially stable deposit money banks at a preferential interest rate known as the minimum rediscount rate (MRR). This rate serves as the baseline for the money market interest rates (acting as a nominal anchor), thereby impacting credit availability, the level of savings (which in turn affects reserves and monetary aggregates), and investment supply, ultimately influencing full employment and GDP growth (Ozsoz et al 2017).

Cash Reserve Ratio: The Central Bank can mandate that deposit money banks maintain a portion of their deposit liabilities as reserves, either as vault cash or deposits with the apex bank. By enforcing fractional reserves, the central bank restricts the amount of loans banks can extend to the economy, thereby controlling the overall money supply. This policy relies on the assumption that banks typically maintain a stable ratio between their reserves and the credit they provide to the public (CBN, 2018).

Exchange Rate: Exchange rate management is a key monetary policy instrument employed by the CBN. Alasha (2020) explains that the exchange rate represents the value of domestic currency, such as the Naira, relative to foreign currencies, like the US dollar. The responsibility for setting and regulating the exchange rate rests solely with the apex bank. As Anifowose (2021) notes, the CBN implements a balanced surveillance system that intervenes in the foreign exchange market to maintain exchange rates around predetermined targets. Khandare (2017) further emphasizes that stable exchange rates promote economic stability, as an appreciation in a country’s currency enhances foreign exchange reserves, supporting economic growth. Consequently, maintaining a stable exchange rate strengthens economic stability and improves the country’s competitiveness in the global market.

Lending Interest Rate: The balance of payments may either be in surplus or deficit, and each scenario influences the monetary base, thereby affecting the overall money supply. To manage this, the Central Bank intervenes in the foreign exchange market by buying or selling foreign currency to maintain exchange rates at levels that prevent undesirable changes in the domestic money supply. Misalignment of the real exchange rate can negatively impact the current account balance by reducing a country’s external competitiveness, highlighting the importance of coordinated exchange rate and balance of payments management in sustaining economic stability.

Financial Resilience

Financial resilience refers to the capacity of individuals or commercial banks to withstand financial shocks or recover effectively from financial difficulties (McKnight & Rucci, 2020). In the context of banking institutions, it encompasses the ability to absorb unexpected financial stress, maintain stability, and continue operations despite adverse economic conditions. Financial resilience ensures that banks can sustain liquidity, manage credit risks, and meet obligations to depositors and stakeholders even during periods of economic downturns. Beyond individual institutions, financial resilience contributes to the broader stability of the financial system, reducing systemic risks and safeguarding the economy from potential crises. As such, it is a key focus area for regulators, policymakers, and financial market participants seeking to enhance the robustness of the banking sector.

Operational resilience, however, has emerged as an equally, if not more, critical aspect of modern banking. It relates to a financial institution’s ability to continue delivering essential services during and

after operational disruptions, including cyberattacks, system failures, or other business interruptions. Financial Market Infrastructure (FMI) firms and regulators worldwide are increasingly evaluating how institutions identify critical business functions, mitigate operational risks, and recover from disruptions. The absence of operational resilience can trigger financial instability, amplifying volatility across markets and potentially undermining public confidence in the financial system. Consequently, regulators require banks to demonstrate their preparedness and resilience for critical services, ensuring continuity, minimizing disruption, and protecting the broader economy from cascading impacts of operational failures.

Theoretical Review

Neoclassical Growth Theory

Neoclassical Growth theory is based on the following:

$$Y(t) = F\{k(t), A(t)L(t)\} \dots \dots \dots (2.3)$$

Where Y is output, k is physical capital, A is an index of overall productivity and L is labour force. with this assumptions, income growth can come from increases efficiency of productive inputs, A or augmentation of inputs k and L. positive growth rates can be sustained if and only if the decreasing returns to accumulation of k are offset by increase in labour force/ human capital L or if the marginal productivity of capital is constantly shifted upwards by technical progress in a balance growth e.g. there will be no depreciation of capital stock and assuming A(t) as constant, output will grow at the rate of human capital. Difference in time of the scale factor A(t) explain countries differences in growth experience. This exogenous source of growth has been interpreted as technical progress. Policy has little scope in affecting long run growth in this setting. Investment and savings impact on the level of per capita income but have no effect on the long run growth rate (Howard & Brian, 2005).

The reason for adopting this theory is because the Nigerian economy can be considered to be at less than full employment level of employment. It is expected that a reduction in the interest rate will make the credit to private sector to increase and therefore investment and hence, growth in the output of the sectors of the economy.

Empirical Review

Erhijakpor and Karevu (2024) analyzed how the interest rate spread (IRS) influenced the financial stability of publicly listed Nigerian banks between 2007 and 2021. Their research explored the effects of lending rates, deposit rates, and the overall rate differential on the resilience of these institutions. Data were drawn from the World Bank (2021), the Securities and Exchange Commission annual report (2021), and the CBN Statistical Bulletin (2021). Employing a census sampling method, the authors included all 21 commercial banks quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group as of 31 December 2021. Findings revealed that the cost and rate of deposits had a positive (coef = 0.056833) yet statistically insignificant (p = 0.5327) relationship with banks' financial soundness, measured by the Z-score.

In a related inquiry, Ariwa (2023) assessed the association between the interest rate spread and the performance of Nigerian DMBs from 2007 to 2020. The study examined PAT, ROE, and ROA as performance indicators, utilizing a panel fixed-effects regression model. Results demonstrated that IRS exerted a significant effect on PAT and ROE but not on ROA.

Similarly, Afrogha et al. (2023) investigated the interplay between monetary policy instruments and the financial performance of Nigerian DMBs over the 1990–2020 period. Their analysis highlighted the centrality of monetary policy in determining the profitability and overall performance of commercial banks in Nigeria.

In the Indonesian context, Aulia and Aisyah (2023) explored how financing, inflation, and money supply affect the profitability of Islamic banks. Relying on secondary data covering 2012–2021 for eight banks registered with the Financial Services Authority, they employed multiple linear regression using SPSS 25. The results showed that, individually, financing, inflation, and money supply variables did not significantly influence ROA. However, when considered jointly, these variables exhibited a collective impact on Islamic banks' profitability.

Focusing again on Nigeria, Oluwayemisi and Fajuyagbe (2022) examined how interest rates—proxied by domestic money supply growth, lending rates, and inflation—affect the ROA of listed banks. Using an ex-post facto design with panel data analysis, they found that money-supply growth and lending rates positively and significantly influenced bank performance, whereas inflation had a significant negative effect.

Anifowose (2021) analyzed how exchange rates influence Nigeria’s economic growth between 1981 and 2020, applying a nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. The findings indicated that exchange rate movements were positively associated with growth, while inflation exerted a delayed, negative effect on gross domestic product (GDP).

Likewise, Alasha (2020) evaluated the effect of exchange-rate fluctuations on Nigeria’s economic stability from 1980 to 2018 using data from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and National Bureau of Statistics annual reports. Employing OLS estimation, the study underscored the vital role of exchange-rate management in maintaining macroeconomic stability and recommended that the CBN strengthen its exchange-rate policy to curb inflation, improve trade balance, and bolster domestic productivity.

Finally, Osakwe et al. (2019) explored how monetary policy variables—monetary policy rate, Treasury-bill rate, cash-reserve requirement, and money supply—affect the manufacturing sector’s contribution to Nigeria’s GDP. Drawing on 1986–2017 time-series data from the CBN Statistical Bulletin, the authors conducted stationarity tests and applied an ARDL model. Their results revealed that monetary policy tools significantly impacted manufacturing output in the short run.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the Ex-Post Facto research design, which is suitable for examining conditions or variables that existed in the past, making it appropriate for the focus of this research. The population for the study comprises the entire Nigerian banking industry, and given the study’s comprehensive scope, the sample size is equivalent to the population. Consequently, the study employed a census sampling technique, which involves using all elements of the population and is considered the most suitable approach for this research.

Secondary data was the primary source of information for this study, as it aligns with the nature of the research topic. Data spanning the period from 1993 to 2022 was collected principally from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and World Bank Group statistical reports (2022). In addition, relevant academic literature, previous studies, articles, and papers were reviewed to complement the data. This approach ensured that the study relied on credible and comprehensive sources to capture trends and patterns in CBN stabilization policies and the financial resilience of Nigerian banks.

The study employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to analyze both short-run and long-run effects of CBN stabilization policies on financial resilience. The ARDL approach, as highlighted by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001), is advantageous because it accommodates variables integrated at levels I(0) and I(1), allows different lag lengths for different variables, and requires only a single-equation setup for estimation. Preliminary tests, including the Unit Root Test and ARDL Bounds Test, were conducted to verify stationarity and co-integration among variables. The model’s normality was assessed using the Jarque-Bera statistic, with normally distributed residuals indicated by a bell-shaped histogram and a probability value exceeding the 5% significance level. The model specified real GDP as a function of Lending Rate (LER), Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Exchange Rate (EXR), and Broad Money Supply (BMS), following the framework of Ekechukwu, Mbah, Ozoko, Diele, and Iwu (2021). This operationalization enabled a robust examination of the effect of apex bank intervention policies on the economic stability of Nigeria.

The operational and log form of the model is stated thus:

$$FIR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LER_t + \beta_2 MPR_t + \beta_3 EXR_t + \beta_4 BMS_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

To avoid scaling problem, the model above was logged (ln). The new model is presented in equation 3 below:

$$\ln FIR_t = \beta_0 + \ln(\beta_1 LER_t) + \ln(\beta_2 MPR_t) + \ln(\beta_3 EXR_t) + \ln(\beta_4 BMS_t) + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data collected for this study were analyzed using a combination of statistical and econometric techniques to ensure thorough examination and reliable results. Initially, descriptive statistics were employed to summarize and provide an overview of the data, highlighting trends, central tendencies, and variations. Correlation analysis was then conducted to examine the relationships between the variables and detect potential multicollinearity. The stationarity of the series was assessed using the unit root test, while the long-run relationships among the variables were determined through the ARDL cointegration test. Finally, a robustness check was performed to validate the reliability and consistency of the results. The outcomes of these analyses are presented below.

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics accounts for the mean, minimum, maximum value, standard deviation value, and observations. The result is presented below:

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	FIR	LER	MPR	EXR	BMS
Mean	13.62605	18.01867	12.62900	161.3347	17.37367
Median	14.21635	17.77000	12.37500	132.8250	17.61500
Maximum	20.06930	27.07000	26.90000	448.0000	25.80000
Minimum	5.425530	11.68000	6.000000	21.89000	8.460000
Std. Dev.	4.388052	3.156127	4.030574	116.5053	5.714136
Jarque-Bera	1.970758	4.683329	24.82834	3.973526	3.267530
Probability	0.373298	0.096167	0.000004	0.137139	0.195193
Observations	30	30	30	30	30

Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

Table 1 shows notable variations in the study variables, reflected in the wide differences between their maximum and minimum values. FIR, LER, MPR, EXR, and BMS reported maximum values of 20.06%, 27.07%, 26.90%, and N448, and minimum values of 5.43%, 11.68%, 6%, and 21.89%, respectively. The mean values were 13.63% (FIR), 12.63% (monetary policy rate), N161.33 (exchange rate), 17.37% (broad money supply), and 18.02% (lending rate), with moderate deviations. Overall, the data clustered around their means, highlighting consistency, while the unit root test was performed to assess series stability.

Correlation Analysis

The study employed correlation analysis to assess the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Correlation values range from -1 to 1, where positive values indicate a direct relationship and negative values indicate an inverse relationship. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of Correlation Analysis

	FIR	LER	MPR	EXR	BMS
FIR	1.000000				
LER	-0.670740	1.000000			
MPR	-0.429553	0.367862	1.000000		
EXR	0.481342	-0.126473	-0.039003	1.000000	
BMS	0.644480	-0.134866	-0.112634	0.109194	1.000000

Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

The correlation analysis reported that, exchange rate and broad money supply had positive coefficient values of 0.481342 and 0.644480. This signals that exchange rate and broad money supply are positively correlated with financial resilience. However, such relationship is moderate. Meanwhile, lending rate and monetary policy rate had a moderate negative relationship with financial resilience.

In terms of the relationship among the study variables, none exhibited high correlation signaling that the possibility of multicollinearity problem is very low. This assertion was reaffirmed by the variance inflation factors reported in table 3 with variance inflation factors' value all less than 10 benchmark for

affirming that none of the variables exhibit presence of multicollinearity problems. More so, the tolerance value (VIF reciprocal) is below 0.10 suggesting that, the series are free from multicollinearity problems.

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factors

	MPR	EXR	BMS	FIR	Average
VIF	1.3035	2.9287	3.8961	2.2014	2.5824
TOV	0.7671	0.3415	0.2567	0.4543	0.4549

Note: TOV= Tolerance Value

Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

Unit Root Test

The unit root test was used to test if the series are stationary or not. They are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of Unit Root Test

ADF at Level-1(0)				
Study Variables	ADF test statistic	Test critical values	Prob.*	Decision
FIR	-2.110582	-2.951125	0.2422	Non-stationary
LER	-3.153068	-2.951125	0.0320	Stationary
MPR	-3.541728	-2.951125	0.0127	Stationary
EXR	2.406791	-2.951125	0.9999	Non-stationary
BMS	-0.751634	-2.951125	0.8195	Non-stationary
ADF at First Difference-1(1)				
Study Variables	ADF test statistic	Test critical values	Prob.*	Decision
FIR	-8.305378	-2.954021	0.0000	Stationary
LER	-7.147804	-2.954021	0.0000	Stationary
MPR	-5.316696	-2.954021	0.0001	Stationary
EXR	-3.539020	-2.954021	0.0130	Stationary
BMS	-5.196432	-2.954021	0.0002	Stationary

Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

The ADF test results in Table 4 indicate that only the monetary policy rate and lending rate were stationary at their levels (I(0)), while the remaining variables achieved stationarity after first differencing (I(1)). This conclusion is based on the fact that their ADF test statistics exceeded the critical values at the natural level. This finding implies that the series are not spurious and are suitable for predictive analysis. Given the mixed order of integration among the variables, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds cointegration test was considered more appropriate than the Johansen cointegration test for examining the long-run relationships between the dependent and independent variables.

ARDL (Bounds) Test for Long run Cointegration

The Bound test examined cointegration between monetary policy tools (LER, MPR, EXR and BMS) and economic stability (RGDP). An F-statistic above the 5% critical bounds rejects the null of no long-run relationship, while values below suggest acceptance. Results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: ARDL Bounds Test for Cointegration

Sample: 1994 2022		
Included observations: 29		
Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist		
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	4.757682	5
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

Table 5 shows that the F-statistic value of 4.757682 exceeds the 5% critical bounds at both I(0) and I(1), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates a long-run relationship among the variables, suggesting that CBN intervention policies have a lasting impact on Nigeria’s economic growth.

Robustness Test

To ensure that the model best fits prediction, the model was further subjected to Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey and Ramsey RESET Test. The results are presented below:

Table 6: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.305215	Prob. F(5,23)	0.9047
Obs*R-squared	1.804455	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.8755
Scaled explained SS	1.116283	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.9527

Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity test in Table 6 yielded an F-statistic probability of 0.9047, indicating that the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity cannot be rejected. Consequently, there is no evidence of heteroskedasticity, meaning the variance of the error term is constant. This confirms that the model is reliable and suitable for prediction.

Table 7: Ramsey RESET Test

Omitted Variables: Squares of fitted values

	Value	Df	Probability
t-statistic	0.153886	25	0.8789
F-statistic	0.023681	(1, 25)	0.8789

Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

The Ramsey Reset Test in table 7 reported a F-statistics probability value of 0.8789 suggests that the null hypothesis of no Omitted Variables holds true. In this wise, the study conclude that variables are well-specified. Meanwhile, the normality test in figure 1 confirmed that, the model is normally distributed.

Figure 1: Normality Test

Source: E-Views version 9.0 (2025)

To properly place the model, the regression result is divided into short and long run while accounting for the Akaike Information Criteria. The results are presented in the following sub-sections.

Akaike Information Criteria

Figure 2: Akaike Information Criteria Test
Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

The Akaike Information Criteria test evidenced that the ARDL Lag selection of ARDL(1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0) is most appropriate for the study.

Regression Results

Table 8 and 9 accounts for the short run and long run ARDL estimates

Short Run Estimates of the Model: The Autoregressive distributive lag model estimates both the short and long run forms of the model. The short run estimates are summarized below:

Table 8: ARDL Cointegrating Result

Dependent Variable: FIR
 Selected Model: ARDL(1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)
 Sample: 1994 2022
 Included observations: 29

Cointegrating Form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LER)	-0.1862	0.0647	-2.8779	0.0104
D(MPR)	-0.6439	0.2088	-3.0845	0.0067
D(EXR)	0.1591	0.0708	2.2477	0.0382
D(BMS)	0.0922	0.1701	0.5421	0.5941
CointEq(-1)	-0.2268	0.0506	-4.4795	0.0003

Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

From the table 8 evidenced that the model has an ARDL Lag selection of ARDL(1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0). Meanwhile, the Error Correction coefficient (cointEq-1) is estimated at -0.2268 and a p-value of 0.0003. This means that the model corrects its previous periods disequilibrium at a speed of 43.35% estimated annually. In other words, if Central Bank of Nigerian stabilization policies are increased steadily on annual bases at 22.68 will improve the financial resilience of Nigerian banking industry. For purposes of clarity, the individual results were tested and discussed in the next sections.

Long Run Estimates of the Model: The long run estimates are summarized in table 9:

Table 9: Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LER	-0.3690	0.0779	-4.7336	0.0001
MPR	-0.4416	0.1395	-3.1652	0.0051
EXR	0.6758	0.3123	2.1637	0.0434
BMS	0.0952	0.1092	0.8723	0.3939
C	1.5951	0.2611	6.1098	0.0000
R-squared	0.6312	Mean dependent var		13.905
Adjusted R-squared	0.5697	S.D. dependent var		4.1860
F-statistic	10.2686	Durbin-Watson stat		2.0823
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0001			

Source: E-Views Version 9.0 (2025)

Table 9 shows that the model's intercept of 6.1098 indicates that if all CBN stabilization policies are held constant, the Nigerian banking industry would maintain a financial resilience score of 6.1098. The R-squared value of 0.6312, supported by an adjusted R² of 0.6312, suggests that the combined effects of LER, MPR, EXR, and BMS explain 63.12% of the variation in FIR, while the remaining 36.88% is captured by the error term, highlighting the model's strong predictive power. The model's statistical significance is confirmed by a Prob.(F-statistic) of 0.0001. Furthermore, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.0823 indicates no evidence of serial correlation. These results demonstrate that the CBN stabilization policies collectively exert a significant impact on the financial resilience of Nigerian banks. The effects of individual variables are examined in the following section.

The results indicate that LER has a significant negative effect on the financial resilience of Nigerian banks in both the short and long run. This implies that higher lending rates increase the cost of credit, discouraging borrowing, and reducing investment in the banking sector. The finding aligns with the Neoclassical Growth Theory, which posits that economic growth can be stimulated by the efficient allocation of productive inputs, particularly capital (k) and labor (L). High lending rates constrain capital accumulation, thereby slowing sectoral growth. Empirically, Erhijakpor and Karevu (2024) and Oluwayemisi and Fajuyagbe (2022) also found that interest rate spreads and lending rates significantly influence bank performance, confirming the current study's results. Ariwa (2023) further notes that lending rates impact profitability metrics such as PAT and ROE, reinforcing the adverse implications of high rates for financial resilience.

The MPR similarly exhibited a negative and statistically significant effect on financial resilience. A higher MPR raises borrowing costs for banks and customers, reducing credit availability to the productive sector, which can hamper output growth. The Neoclassical Growth Theory emphasizes that productivity (A) and input utilization are key determinants of growth, suggesting that policy-induced constraints on credit supply can dampen sectoral performance. Empirical studies by Afrogha, Tyohen, and Afrogha (2023) and Oluwayemisi and Fajuyagbe (2022) confirm that monetary policy tools, including MPR, significantly shape bank performance in Nigeria. The short-run impact observed mirrors Osakwe et al. (2019), who found that monetary policy interventions significantly influence sectoral output in the short term.

EXR exhibited a positive effect on financial resilience, though the relationship was moderate. A stable or appreciating domestic currency enhances banks' ability to mobilize and deploy resources effectively, supporting sectoral growth and stability. According to Neoclassical Growth Theory, technological progress and efficient utilization of resources determine long-term output growth; a stable exchange rate strengthens macroeconomic conditions, facilitating productive investment. This finding is consistent with Anifowose (2021) and Alasha (2020), who report that a favorable exchange rate positively affects economic growth and stability. Empirically, it also aligns with Osakwe et al. (2019), who emphasize the importance of monetary stability in promoting sectoral output.

BMS was found to have a positive effect on financial resilience, although its short-run effect was insignificant. Expanding liquidity in the banking system enhances credit availability, encourages investment, and fosters output growth, consistent with Neoclassical Growth Theory where input augmentation (capital and labor) drives growth. This is supported by empirical studies such as Aulia and

Aisyah (2023), which found that money supply positively influences bank profitability, and Osakwe et al. (2019), who observed that monetary interventions increase sectoral output in the short run.

Overall, the findings confirm that CBN stabilization policies significantly influence the financial resilience of Nigerian banks. Lending and monetary policy rates exert a constraining effect, while exchange rate stability and broad money supply support resilience. The results are consistent with both the theoretical predictions of Neoclassical Growth Theory and prior empirical evidence, highlighting the importance of balanced monetary interventions to foster sustainable growth and financial stability.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of CBN stabilization policy on the financial resilience the Nigerian banking industry from 1993 to 2022. Specifically, the study examined the effect of lending rate, monetary policy rate, exchange rate and broad money supply ratio on financial resilience of the Nigerian banking industry. Accordingly, four research hypotheses were postulated. Based on the major findings of the study, the study concludes that, lower lending rate, lower monetary policy rate and moderate exchange rate improve the financial resilience of the Nigerian banking industry on both the short and long run.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the various findings stated in chapter four and the conclusion stated in chapter five, the following policy recommendations were made:

- i. The Central Bank of Nigeria should adjust the benchmark interest rates using a relatively stable monetary policy rates. Also, the Central Bank of Nigeria should focus on maintaining its lending rate at a low rate (if possible single digit) and ensure that the rate is stable.
- ii. The Central Bank of Nigeria should ensure that the current monetary policy rate should be reconsidered since it has a potential impact on the financial resilience of the Nigerian banking industry.
- iii. The Central Bank of Nigeria advocated should adjust interest rates to influence currency value. This is because a moderate lending rate will attract foreign investment, increasing demand for the currency and potentially strengthening its value.
- iv. Efforts should be made to increase the supply of funds to the Nigerian economy. This is because broad money supply exerted positive significant effect on economic stability both on the short and long run.

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